

Dissemination and communication plan

D 4.1 / 30.04.24

Document Overview

Title	D 4.1 / Dissemination and communication plan
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Submission date	30/04/2024
Version	1.0 30/04/2024
Dissemination level	Public
Work Package	WP4 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

ECLECTIC Enabling circular economy action plans for small and medium-sized cities is a project funded by Formas, FCT, LMT and MUR under the Driving Urban Transitions Partnership, which has been co-funded by the European Union.

Revision History

Date	Version	Author	Description
27-03-2024	v.01	Ludovica Galeazzi	First full draft of the deliverable
22-04-2024	v.02	Sergio Caetano, Beatriz Pereira	Review and integration of content
30-04-2024	v.03	Ludovica Galeazzi, Chiara Pellegrini	Final review and formatting

About the project

Cities concentrate high density socio-economic activities, consuming 70% of global resources, producing 60-80% of anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and generating waste of resources, energy and water. This is a critical issue, but at the same time it offers opportunities.

Circular economy models can reduce this waste and reduce human environmental impacts.

Eclectic brings circular economy from theory to action in cities, by improving the understanding of cities as complex multi-level ecosystems with inputs, outputs, and resource flows. The project designs, implements, and monitors strategic action plans for circular economy in cities, taking care to address vulnerable groups and to reduce inequality in selecting circular models.

Four city-region living labs (CiRLabs) located in Italy, Lithuania, Sweden and Portugal will be the testing sites where the circular practices will be implemented. In the CiRLabs, stakeholder engagement processes will be the means to identify needs and visions for CE, and to select CE actions that fit them. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be defined to measure and monitor the effectiveness of the selected circular economy action plans.

Outputs from the project will include four scientific papers, three reports, four actionable reports, a toolbox, workshops, and trainings.

Project partners

Executive Summary

Communication and dissemination are key activities for Eclectic since they are means to raise awareness and transfer knowledge to audiences that may benefit from the project's outcomes. Eclectic aims to communicate and disseminate information on the project and related activities, events, and outcomes among stakeholders and citizens interest in circular economy (CE); to disseminate and foster the exploitation of project results, of the tools, metrics, data, and recommendations; to provide educational and training materials on the project and on just & inclusive circular city-regions; to facilitate engagement of follower cities and replication of the project outcomes in other urban contexts.

This document is a communication and dissemination plan: a strategic document that outlines how information about Eclectic will be shared with its target audience. This document has two main purposes:

1. To be a guide for project partners to effectively communicate the outcomes of the project, to reach, engage and involve the stakeholders and to contribute to the advancement of the discourse around circular economy.
2. To provide an explanation of the processes that led to the communication and dissemination choices and to the analysis of their outcomes. It aims to be a resource for other projects wishing to engage similar targets in similar processes related to CE.

This document is published in a first version at M6 (April 2024) and it will be updated during the project life to align and effectively disseminate the project outcomes and results as they emerge.

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Term	Description
CE	Circular Economy
CiRLab	City-Region Living Lab
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DUT	Driving Urban Transitions Partnership
EU	European Union
GIS	Geographical Information System
H	How
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life-Cycle Assessment
MFA	Material Flow Accounting
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
UM	Urban Metabolism
W	What
WP	Work Package

1 Branding process

The brand identity is how the project Eclectic will come across to stakeholders. A great brand identity is:

1. Recognisable and unique: the brand incorporates distinctive visual elements and a logo, to make Eclectic stand out among other projects.
2. Relevant: the brand identity reflects the project's content, that is its approach to circular economy in cities, aligning visual elements with the project's content.
3. Accessible and simple: a brand identity that is not only visually appealing but also easy to read and understand.

To start the branding process, Eurac Research held an online workshop with the project partners.

The workshop focused on two aspects:

1. Defining the brand personality
2. Exploring the audiences

WP4: 1 - Brand personality

If ECLECTIC was...

...a **car**, which kind of car would it be?

FIAT - RED, New Fiat 500 electric (city drive), JEEP, Volkswagen Multivan (including city carshare), UAZ 452, TESLA, 500, Subaru, subaru, Ferrari, electric, Volvo

...an **animal**, which kind of animal would it be?

DOG, ANT, tiger, GOAT, zebro, Fox, Horse, Mouse, Bee, pig, bee, CAT, Pig

...a **month**, which month would it be?

JULY, MARCH, sept, May, June, February, MARCH, JANUARY, May, April, march, March, may

...a **celebrity**, which celebrity would it be?

PICASSO, Taylor Swift, CHRIS MARTIN, Brad Pitt, Amal Clonney, Oprah, Tom Hanks, Di caprio, beyonce, Leonardo di caprio, Miley Cyrus, Da Vinci

...a **word**, which word would it be? *

Happiness, connection, Positivity, Resources, Inclusion, symbiosis, collaborative, Lunar - Moon, Fascination, Renewable, full immersion, Forward-looking

* **Forbidden words:** innovative-innovation, sustainable-sustainability, circular-circularity, economy, project, research, european-Europe, international, future, green.

Figure 1: Brand personality exercise – part 1

Figure 2: Brand personality exercise – part 2

The two exercises provided the basis to define the 5 dimensions of the brand, 5 words that illustrate how the brand should look, feel, and behave.

Figure 3: Five dimensions of the brand

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The 5 words chosen are:

- **Community oriented:** Eclectic places a strong emphasis on engaging and involving communities, developing processes that resonates with the needs of the people living in the urban and regional areas under study.
- **Synergic:** Eclectic recognizes that to advance circular economy practices in city-regions requires a combined effort from various stakeholders, and only through collaboration can meaningful change be achieved.
- **Inclusive:** Eclectic prioritizes diversity including a wide range of voices and the active engagement of vulnerable groups in its research to reduce inequality in circular economy processes.
- **Expert:** Eclectic is commitment to evidence-based research, aiming to set a standard of excellence in its research methodologies.
- **Positive:** Eclectics look on the future is optimistic, emphasizing that the implementation of circular economy strategies has the power to transform cities in better.

These words serve as guiding principles, as a compass, aligning all communication efforts with the core identity of the project.

2 Brand identity

The branding exercises allowed the graphic designer to understand the features of the logo and identity of Eclectic.

During the design process, the designer aimed at answering four needs.

- **Appropriateness:** does the style make sense for the audience of the project?
- **Distinction:** does it stand out in a crowd? Is it memorable?
- **Simplicity:** is it clear enough and easily understandable by stakeholders?
- **Versatility:** is it able to adapt to the various design applications?

Particularly important is the friendly appearance, conveying a sense of inclusivity and synergy. It should also communicate expertise and positivity, making use of clean lines and shapes, bright and refreshing colours associated with the concepts of rebirth and growth.

During the project meeting in Bolzano, held on the 1st of February 2024, three proposals were presented, playing with geometric shapes and lines to convey several concepts of circularity.

Version 1

Version 2

Version 3

Figure 4: Preliminary proposals of the Eclectic logo.

Following the feedback from the partners, the logo underwent further development to reach the final version. Different geometric shapes manage to “close the loop”, conveying the message that materials can be transformed and become new resources.

Closing the loop...

...with **different components**,
transforming resources,
that **become something else**
and part of the whole

Figure 5: Eclectic logo concept

Figure 6: Eclectic logo, different versions, with and without payoff.

The colour palette differentiates the logo from other brands of the circular economy sector. The primary colours are shades of dark and light blue. Secondary colours remind to the concepts of sustainability and green. The red accent highlights the innovative aspect of the project.

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Figure 7: Eclectic colour palette

The font used is Raleway, with rounded lettering which match the rounded shapes of the logo. The font is freely downloadable at the link <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Raleway>.

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HEADINGS

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INTRO TEXT

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TITLES

Raleway Bold, Dark Blue

BODY TEXT

Raleway Regular, Black

NOTES AND CAPTIONS

Raleway Regular, Dark Blue

Figure 8: Eclectic typography

The brand identity has been applied to design the first project poster, used during the DUT Conference organised in Brussels in April 2024.

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Figure 9: Eclectic project poster

The brand identity will be declined in project reports and presentations, as well as in communication materials that will be created during the project.

This brainstorming session is the basis for the definition of the **objectives of the communication** and dissemination activities, regarding each audience, and for the **definition of the key messages**.

Table 1: Eclectic Target audience

Audience	Problem/Desire	Communication objectives	Approaches
1 Local authorities and policymakers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of knowledge about which circular economy solutions can be put in practice. 2. Lack of knowledge of how to measure circularity. 3. Lack of understanding of the environmental and economic value and the impacts of waste. 4. Would like to know how to engage with citizens and stakeholders to Implement/activate circular economy processes. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Raise awareness. 2. Increase knowledge (2-4) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Branding • Storytelling • Reports and data dissemination • Toolbox dissemination • Trainings and workshops • Networking
2 Policymakers at national level	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of concrete knowledge and validated success stories backed by data to create regulations for circular economy at national level 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reports, factsheets and data dissemination
3 Associations of local and regional governments	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Would like to make circular economy a reality, but lack of skills and knowledge 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Branding • Toolbox dissemination

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Trainings and workshops ● Networking
<p>4 Local and regional business and industry associations</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of knowledge of what circular economy concretely means. 2. Lack of knowledge and skills to adapt infrastructure (from linear to circular). 3. Lack of understanding of the local economy and see opportunities to implement circular economy. 4. Lack of knowledge on the supply chain and on how to close the value chains. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Raise awareness. 2. Increase knowledge (2-4) 3. Motivating change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Branding ● Storytelling ● Trainings and workshops ● Networking
<p>5 Urban planners</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of knowledge of what circular economy concretely means and successful case studies. 2. Lack of knowledge on how to build or restructure the current infrastructure, in order to be more effective in supporting circular economy processes. 3. Lack of awareness on the effects of infrastructure on circular economy 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Raise awareness. 2. Increase knowledge. 3. Motivating change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Branding ● Storytelling ● Toolbox dissemination ● Trainings and workshops

<p>6 National and local waste management and recycling companies</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of knowledge of what CE concretely means. 2. Want to know governance models and interface between private and public sector. 3. Need to make their process known to firms to find circular economy implementation opportunities. 4. Need to raise awareness among citizens of correct waste and recycling processes. 5. Need to detect profitable CE processes. 6. Are afraid to reduce waste and have less income. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Raise awareness (1-4) 2. Increase knowledge. (2-3-5) 3. Motivating to change (3-6) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Branding • Storytelling • Trainings and workshops • Networking
<p>7 Associations dealing with circular economy / Regional and local circular economy influencers</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Need content and success stories that are reliable and scientifically backed 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Branding • Storytelling • Reports and data dissemination • Toolbox dissemination
<p>8 Researchers / Academia</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Want to contribute to academic discourse about CE. 2. Need to show how to create effective circular economy processes. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase knowledge (provide tools and trainings) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications • Reports and data dissemination

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Toolbox dissemination
<p>9 Citizens and citizens' associations</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Have no knowledge of circular economy and CE opportunities. 2. Not feeling empowered and involved in CE implementation. 3. Difficult to find second hand/repair/recycle places/shops. 4. Lack of a simple way to detect "circularity" (labelling). 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Raise awareness. 2. Increase knowledge (2-4) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Branding • Storytelling • Trainings and workshops

From a first assessment, it results that the main issue is the lack of knowledge about circular economy. We are in the following situation.

Marketing Funnel in Practice

Figure 11: Marketing funnel [1]

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Stakeholders (except research/academia and associations) are in the higher part of the funnel: either they are not aware of the opportunities of circular economy, or they are aware but they have no clear understanding of it.

The main objective of the communication and dissemination activities of Eclectic should therefore be to **raise awareness**: make circular economy known and understood by the target audiences.

The second objective is to **increase knowledge** for those audiences that already grasp the importance of CE but need concrete examples and best practices to make it real.

The ultimate objective is to drive audiences to **change behaviours**, which may mean to implement circular processes in place of linear processes, or to facilitate the creation of circular economy action plans. This is the equivalent of the "conversion" phase, but it is too premature for Eclectic.

Given the high number of target groups, a prioritization is needed.

The matrix shows the priority of each target group, as it emerged from the brainstorming.

Priority has been given to

- **Local authorities and policymakers**
- **Local and regional business and industry associations**
- **National and local waste management and recycling companies**

These are the most important audiences that can influence the adoption of CE processes and that already manifest an interest towards it.

If these audiences are reached and engaged, they will be the sounding board which will enable also to reach a wider group of people, and other audiences.

Audiences in other cells can be engaged with the aim to move in the cells on the right.

Figure 12: Prioritization of target groups

4 Strategy

The table below matches target groups, communication objectives, approaches, and communication activities. Approaches refer to the type of interaction between the communicating subjects and the target groups.

Table 2: Strategy – Objectives, Approaches, Activities

Target group	Communication objective	Approaches	Communication activity
All	Raise awareness	Branding	Creation of a defined and consistent brand identity
All	Raise awareness	Branding	Creation of pages dedicated to the project in each partner website
1, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9	Raise awareness	Storytelling	Collection of success stories and creation of (D2.2) Portfolio 20+ solutions for circular urban transformation.
1, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9	Raise awareness	Storytelling	Dissemination of the (D2.2) Portfolio through partners channels.
1, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9	Raise awareness	Storytelling	Further suggestion: Collection of photos, videos, interviews during CiRLab implementation and disseminate videos through partners' channels.
1, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9	Raise awareness	Storytelling	<i>Further suggestion: creation of local videos in local language from the content of the success stories (D2.2) and disseminate videos via partners' channels.</i>
9	Raise awareness	Storytelling	<i>Further suggestion: Communication campaigns for the citizens adaptable to each country/region characteristics via partners' channels.</i>
1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6	Increase knowledge	Reports and data dissemination	Disseminate guidelines and report for monitoring scheme in cities/region (D2.3) via partners' channels.

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1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6	Increase knowledge	Reports and data dissemination	Disseminate Handbook on policy recommendations to design inclusive and just CE strategies (D3.3) via partners' channels.
1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6	Increase knowledge	Reports and data dissemination	Disseminate Report on lesson learned from co-selection of CE strategies in the CiRLabs (D2.4) via partners' channels.
1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6	Increase knowledge	Reports and data dissemination	Disseminate the Report on entrepreneurship & business innovation for circular urban transformation (D2.3) via partners' channels.
1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6	Increase knowledge	Reports and data dissemination	Creation and dissemination of infographic and data-storytelling via partners' channels.
8	Increase knowledge	Scientific publications	Disseminate the results of scientific papers D1.1, D1.2 D3.1, D3.2 via partners' channels.
8	Increase knowledge	Scientific publications	Presentation at scientific conferences
1, 3, 5, 6, 7	Increase knowledge	Toolbox dissemination	Disseminate the toolbox via partners' channels.
1, 3, 5, 7	Increase knowledge	Trainings and workshops	Organize regional in-person trainings on the use of the Toolbox.
1, 3, 5, 7	Increase knowledge	Storytelling	<i>Further suggestion: Collect feedback about toolbox usage in form of video interviews and disseminate in via partners' channels.</i>
1, 3, 5, 7	Increase knowledge	Trainings and workshops	Organize Webinar with CiRLabs and follower cities network (D4.2) and disseminate content via partners' channels.

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1, 3, 5, 7	Increase knowledge	Trainings and workshops	Organize Online workshop with follower cities network (D4.3) and disseminate content via partners' channels.
1, 3, 4, 6, 7	Raise awareness	Networking	Presentation at regional, national, international events tailored to policymakers, authority, and SMEs
1, 3, 4, 6, 7	Raise awareness	Networking	Dissemination via the partners contacts, institutions, professional networks, professional representations, interest groups
1, 2, 3	Increase knowledge	Networking	Promotion of the policy suggestions through Covenant of Mayors, DUT meetings and EU institutions

This list is intended to guide the consortium WP 4 team in the management of the communication and dissemination activities.

5 Key Messages

Key messages explain complex information in **clear and easily understandable statements**. They will convey the ideas and objectives of Eclectic, ensuring that target groups grasp the key takeaways.

As Eclectic is a research project, findings of the project are still unknown and stakeholder research is still ongoing. Clarity about these two aspects is important to develop the correct messages. Therefore, what we list here is a draft of the key messages, that will need to be refined as the project goes on.

The **draft messages** were validated during the first project meeting in Bolzano held on the 1st and 2nd of February 2024 and can be found in Table 3.

Table 3: Key messages

Audience	Key messages
1 Local authorities and policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eclectic shows the best practices of 20 CE success stories from small and medium-sized EU cities. • Eclectic provides a monitoring scheme for assessing and measuring circular economy action plans. • Eclectic analyses the flow of materials and waste in city regions, and quantifies the environmental impact of waste through a UM-LCA model that will support the design of circular economy action plans. • Eclectic will provide knowledge resources for citizen engagement and effective participants approaches to circular economy. The Eclectic toolbox will enable easier citizens engagement.
2 Policymakers at national level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eclectic provides reports in local languages about the project outputs, experiences and stories.
3 Associations of local and regional governments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eclectic provides case studies on successful circular economy practices.
4 Local and regional business and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eclectic provides a taxonomy and shows the best practices of 20 Circular economy success stories of firms and businesses profiting

<p>industry associations</p>	<p>from the CE process implemented. Stories and examples will be local to resonate with local businesses.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through local workshops SMEs and business will learn to rethink "take-make-waste" production models and identify opportunities to "close the loop" (CiRLabs actions). • Eclectic provides a UM-LCA model that can be applied to each region to characterize cities in terms of resource flows and associated environmental impacts and understand synergies between different sectors. • Eclectic provides opportunities to connect the end of the loop (waste management) and the beginning of the loop (production of new goods).
<p>5 Urban planners</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eclectic provides a taxonomy and concrete examples of circular economy practice that contribute to sustainable, cost-effective urban planning. • Through Eclectic 's study of material flows / transports (GIS data) urban planners can make informed decisions on how to implement circular economy processes in cities.
<p>6 National and local waste management and recycling companies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eclectic provides a taxonomy and concrete examples of circular economy practices that successfully transform waste management practices. • Eclectic provides dialogue opportunities, data, and examples (international and national) that can help spark partnerships between waste management companies and authorities. • Eclectic provides staff of waste management companies with dialogue opportunities with firms to discuss how to reduce recycle and reuse waste materials to produce new goods. • Eclectic works with citizens and citizens' associations through workshops and other activities to educate them about the correct waste disposal and recycling processes.

<p>7 Associations ad NGOs dealing with CE / Regional and local CE influencers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eclectic provides scientifically backed examples of circular economy processes and success stories.
<p>8 Researchers / Academia</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eclectic produces new knowledge and measurement frameworks that can deepen the discourse about circular economy.
<p>9 Citizens and citizens' associations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eclectic provides citizens with a simple explanation of circular economy and success stories they can relate to. • Eclectic works with citizens through workshops, interviews, and surveys to promote their understanding of circular economy. • Eclectic provides transnational and inspirational success local stories, that resonate with citizens. • Circularity is hidden, there is no clear label – Eclectic has no real answer to that but will connect with other initiatives and project researching this topic.

The key messages are what can resonate with the target group and should be kept in mind when communicating and disseminating information with them.

Further developments of the research project will enable us to define the key messages about circular economy.

6 Communication channels

Communication and dissemination activities take place in communication channels, which are the most effective ways to reach and engage the target audience. The selection of communication channels in a communication plan is a strategic decision based on:

- **Target audience:** since different stakeholders have varying preferences for receiving information, communication channels may differ greatly. A mix of channels is an effective way to have a broader reach.
- **Communication objectives:** selected channels should align with the communication objectives. For example, to raise awareness channels with broad reach like social media or press releases may be suitable. For in-depth engagement and training, workshops and publications might be more effective.

6.1 Partners' channels

A key aspect for effective communication is the **availability of partners' channels:** leveraging partners' channels is a cost-effective strategy and makes sure the content is tailored to each **local** audience.

- Instead of building an audience from scratch, Eclectic can benefit from the partners' **established networks**, reaching a larger number of users who are already connected to the partner organizations.
- Information disseminated through partners' channels benefits from the **credibility** associated with those institutions and authorities. Audiences are more likely to engage with and trust the information coming from these sources.
- Partners channels can publish **local** experiences, stories and data, partners channels that resonate with **local** audiences.
- Aligning communication efforts with partners' channels ensures that the project's messages are **consistent** with the goals and values of the partner organizations.
- The **language** used will be in line with the language of each region, making it easier to communicate also to those not familiar with English.

Table 4 lists available partners' channels and their target audience.

Table 4: Partners' channels

Partner	Channels	Link	Followers	Target audience
EURAC	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/renewables-eurac-research/	3000	Academia SMEs Innovative Startups in the field of energy efficiency, e-mobility Local policymakers (South Tyrol) in the field of environment/e energy/transportation Specialized media and press (renewable energy/innovation)
	X	https://twitter.com/EURACrenewables	1500	
	Newsletter Institute for Renewable Energy	tbc (starting May 2024)		
	Website	https://www.eurac.edu/en/institutes-centers/institute-for-renewable-energy		
	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC8A9p6XEyGi3FbAd8Q7AXyQ	30	
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/euracresearch/	22000	Citizens Academia Local policymakers (South Tyrol) Media and press (South Tyrol) Media and press (Italian)
	X	https://twitter.com/EURAC	6000	
	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/eurac.research/	16000	
	Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/euracresearch/	3400	
	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/EURACtv	3500	
	Newsletter Eurac Research			
	Magazine (online)	https://www.eurac.edu/en/magazine		
	Press releases			

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CHALMERS	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/school/chalmers-university-of-technology/	137000	Academia, students, potential students
	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/chalmersuniversityoftechnology/	48000	
	Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/chalmers.university/	14000	
	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/chalmersuniversity	7700	
	TikTok	chalmers.student	370000	Potential students
UC	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/school/universidade-de-coimbra/	131000	Graduating students, alumni, industry professionals
	X	https://twitter.com/UnivdeCoimbra	39000	General academic community
	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/univdecoimbra	219000	Prospective and current students, alumni, faculty, parents, and other members of the academic community
	Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/ucoimbra/	108000	Prospective and current students, young adults
	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwJWYs4uKz77qR_NaruUcBg	20000	Prospective and current students, parents, faculty
	Newsletter	https://www.uc.pt/en/ucglobal		
	Website	https://pages.uc.pt/en/uc-news/		

D 4.1 / Dissemination and communication plan

IPC	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/school/politecnicodecoimbra	7000	Citizens, Academia, Companies, Media and press, Local policymakers
	X	https://twitter.com/IP_Coimbra	174	
	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/PolitecnicodeCoimbra	24000	
	Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/politecnicodecoimbra/	12000	
	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/c/politecnicodecoimbraipc	1240	
	Website (magazine)	https://www.ipc.pt/magazine/		
GOT	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/g%C3%B6teborg/	60000	Citizens, SMEs, local policymakers
	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/goteborgsstad/	41000	
	Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/goteborgsstad/	6000	
	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/goteborgsstad	1960	
CIM-RC	X	https://twitter.com/RegiaodeCoimbra	105	Citizens SMEs Local policymakers Media and press
	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/cimregiaodecoimbra/?locale=pt_PT	16000	
	Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/cimregiaodecoimbra	2500	
	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCbYZ_I7rUqVkkftN56VRAUA	340	
	Website	https://www.cim-regiaodecoimbra.pt/		
	LinkedIn	https://pt.linkedin.com/company/cim-regiao-de-coimbra		Academia, SMEs
APB	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/provincia-autonoma-dibolzano/	8000	Citizens, SMEs, local policymakers

D 4.1 / Dissemination and communication plan

	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ProvinciaBolzano/	32000	
	Website	https://home.provincia.bz.it/it/home		
	Press releases			Local media and press
KTU	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ktuevf	4500	Academia, Citizens SMEs Local policymakers Media and press
	Web site (faculty)	https://seb.ktu.edu/		
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ktu-school-of-economics-and-business/	2000	
	Web site (university)	https://en.ktu.edu/		
	Specific research team	https://circularresearch.ktu.edu/		
JON	Web site	https://jonava.lt/		Citizens, SMES, local policymakers, Media and press
	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/jonavosrajonas		
	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCe0nYtSeHEZgXtSOcRMoeQ		

6.2 Earned media

Earned media refers to **exposure gained through efforts that are not paid for directly**. It includes positive mentions, shares, or coverage of a brand, product, or service by external sources such as journalists, influencers, or customers.

Leveraging earned media can be a powerful way to reach a wider audience and increase the course visibility. Instrumental will be the involvement of partners and lecturers, as they hold the contacts with external sources.

Here is an overview of potential earned media, to be further updated as the project goes on.

Table 5: Earned media

Partner responsible	External media	Target	Content interested in
Eurac Research	NOI Techpark channels (newsletter, social media, website)	Innovative startups, entrepreneurs, researchers and academia, specialized media and press (innovation) Citizens Local media and press (South Tyrol)	Innovation, new business models, case studies
Eurac Research	Rivista CasaClima	Building sector professionals (South Tyrol), innovative building sector firms (Italy)	Building sector initiatives / case studies
Eurac Research	Local South Tyrol TV, magazines, newspapers	Citizens Local policymakers (South Tyrol) Media and press (South Tyrol)	Local initiatives / successful project results / local case studies
Eurac Research	Specialized Italian online magazines in building constructions	Professionals in the building sector - SMEs (Italy)	Circularity in construction
Eurac Research	Build Up	Professionals in the building sector SMEs (Europe)	Circularity in construction
Eurac Research	Covenant of Mayors	Local policymakers and authorities (Europe)	Climate and energy actions for local governments, successful cases studies, policy briefs.

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Eurac Research	ICLEI	Local policymakers and authorities (Europe)	Climate and energy actions for local governments, successful cases studies, policy briefs.
Eurac Research	Europaregio Tirol Südtirol Trentino	Local policymakers and authorities (Tirol Südtirol Trentino)	successful cases studies, policy briefs
Eurac Research	ANCI Associazione nazionale dei comuni italiani	Local policymakers and authorities (Italy)	Successful cases studies, policy briefs
KTU	Association of Local Authorities in Lithuania (ALAL) Lietuvos savivaldybiu asociacija (lsa.lt)	Local policymakers and authorities (Lithuania)	Successful cases studies, policy briefs
KTU	Kaunas Chamber of commerce, industry and crafts (Kaunas and Jonava) chamber.lt	Local industry (Kaunas, Lithuania)	Opportunities for local industry, success stories, trainings
UC	CEC – Chamber of Commerce and Industry of the Center/CCIC https://cec.org.pt/sobre-o-cec-ccic/	Local industry (Coimbra; Portugal)	Opportunities for local industry, success stories, trainings
UC	IPN - business incubator (https://www.ipn.pt/incubadora)	Local industry, innovators (Portugal)	Opportunities for local industry, success stories, trainings
UC	NERC https://nerc.pt/	Local industry (Coimbra; Portugal)	Opportunities for local industry, success stories, trainings
CIM-RC	CCDRC - Center Regional Coordination and Development Commission, I. P. https://www.ccdrc.pt/pt/	Regional Authority	Local events, training opportunities

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CIM-RC	CIM-RC's municipalities social networks	Local authorities (Coimbra; Portugal)	Local success stories, events, training opportunities
CIM-RC	Intermunicipal Council of the CIM Região de Coimbra	Local authorities (Coimbra; Portugal)	Opportunities for the Region, successful cases studies, policy briefs
CIM-RC	Strategic Council for Intermunicipal Development	Relevant stakeholders in the Coimbra region (companies, public institutions and public and private bodies at municipal and regional level)	Opportunities for the Region, successful cases studies, policy briefs

6.3 Project Website

The project website is hosted in Eurac Research's website. Eclectic's webpage will contain published articles and deliverables, once they are publicly available, as well as the toolbox and other communication materials that may be developed during the project.

The Eclectic webpage is available at www.eurac.edu/eclectic.

Figure 13: Eclectic website eurac.edu/ecllectic

Additionally, project partners will publish a page dedicated to Eclectic on their own website.

6.4 Social media and digital channels

While establishing dedicated social media channels and a newsletter for Eclectic may seem like a straightforward approach, leveraging partners' existing channels can offer several advantages.

- An already **established following**.
- Messages can be **tailored** to each region's needs and delivered in **local** language.
- **Credibility and trust** as the institutions are already authorities in their fields.
- **Resource efficiency**: establishing and managing a separate project channel is expensive in time and money and guarantees no results as each country needs specific messages.

The negative point is the absence of a single repository for the communication activity of the project.

However, as it would take time and effort to make the channel effective, the benefits of only **using existing channels** outweigh the drawbacks. For this reason, the choice has been made not to open new channels but rather to exploit existing partners channels.

WP4 team will guide and assist partners in the development of content for their own social media channels and other digital channels.

Figure 14: LinkedIn post on Institute for Renewable Energy – Eurac Research LinkedIn

6.5 Communication materials

WP4's team will provide templates of communication materials that each partner can adapt according to their needs.

This will ensure that partners can use local languages and tailor the message to their audience, while maintaining a consistent identity.

The choice of communication materials will depend mainly on the events that partners will organize or participate in. Further advancement of the project will be necessary to choose the right communication materials.

6.6 Events and conferences

Events and conference are opportunities to amplify the impact of the research findings.

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1. Events are **networking opportunities** to build connections between like-minded people: researchers, policymakers, businesses, local communities, and influencers can come together to discuss best practices and find solutions to advance circular economy in cities.
2. Events are the place for **knowledge exchange**: Eclectic's partners can present their results and can get to know the latest developments, challenges, and success stories from others committed to driving sustainable and just urban development.
3. **New collaborations** can spark: Eclectic's partners can explore potential partnerships with municipalities, businesses, research institutions, and associations, to further spread circular economy implementation in cities.

An Excel file has been setup to encourage partners to share events that they plan to attend, or to brainstorm potential dissemination opportunities.

The organization of the following two events is already planned:

1. D4.2. Webinar with CiRLabs and follower cities network in M18
2. D.4.3 online workshop with follower cities network in M32

WP4 team will guide and assist partners in the participation of events, providing communication materials, tips for effective promotion of the event and post-event storytelling, which will be activities done in partners own media.

6.6.1 Event toolkit

A standard event toolkit, customisable for each event, will be provided containing:

- Template for event poster
- Template for LinkedIn banner
- Template for YouTube cover (for digital events)
- Templates of press releases
- Template of media/stakeholder invitation
- Photo gallery
- Video gallery (if available)
- Check list for communication activities to be done prior to, during, and after the event.

6.7 Reports

The reports planned for the Eclectic project play a crucial role in achieving the communication objectives of increasing knowledge among the target groups. Six reports are planned, in the table below we match reports with the target groups.

Table 6: Reports

Deliverable number	Deliverable name	WP	Delivery date	Target group
D2.1	Strategic plan for stakeholder engagement	2	M6	1, 3
D2.2	Portfolio of 20+ solutions for circular urban transformation	2	M12	1, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9
D2.3	Report on entrepreneurship & business innovation for circular urban transformation	2	M30	1,4, 5, 6
D2.4	Report on lesson learned from co-selection of CE strategies in the CiRLabs	2	M32	1,2
D3.3	Handbook on policy recommendations to design inclusive and just CE strategies	3	M34	1,2
D1.3	Guidelines and report for monitoring scheme in cities/regions	1	M36	1,4,5,6

Further details on the dissemination of reports will be given after they are published.

6.8 Toolbox

The toolbox main aim is to **collect in one place the tools, metrics and recommendations** that will allow public authorities, local administrators, and policymakers to design, implement, and monitor circular economy action plans. The aim will be to foster replication and exploitation of results, by follower cities and key urban stakeholders across small & medium EU cities.

The target of the toolbox will be:

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- Local authorities and policymakers
- Researchers

The toolbox will be in English and translated in partners' languages, and disseminated through the project websites, and partners channels such as social media, through press releases and personal contacts to key stakeholders.

Further details will be provided once the toolbox development advances.

6.9 Scientific publications

Eclectic is a research project: therefore, scientific publications are cornerstone in communication and dissemination strategy, for several reasons.

- **Publications are means of knowledge transfer:** researchers can effectively communicate methodologies and results to researchers and professionals in the field of circular economy.
- **Published research has the potential to influence policy development:** policymakers often refer to scientific literature for evidence-based decision-making, and practitioners use research findings to inform their strategies and actions.
- **Scientific publications contribute to the creation of a long-term knowledge legacy:** by documenting research methodologies and results, the understanding and advancement of circular economy concepts are preserved for future researchers and practitioners.

Four publications are planned, further details on their dissemination will be given after they are published.

Table 7: Scientific publications

Deliverable number	Deliverable name	WP	Delivery date
D3.1	Scientific paper on household characteristics and consumption patterns	3	M20
D1.1	Scientific article on UM-LCA analysis and comparison across cities/regions	1	M21
D3.2	Scientific paper on household consumption and sharing practice's drivers, habits, and vulnerabilities	3	M25
D1.2	Scientific article on CE strategies potential	1	M30

6.10 Zenodo

To publish all the deliverables, report, publications, dataset produced during the project, a Zenodo community has been created: <https://zenodo.org/communities/eclectic>

The Zenodo community will be the main repository of the project and it will be connected to the project website.

7 Storytelling

On the long run the people interested in why you do something and how you do it, might decide to buy what you do - your idea or product. [2]

Storytelling is a great way to connect emotionally with an audience and at the same time explain what the problem is, the solution and what can they do to be a part of the change. It is a process to present a topic as a **story**.

Stories must follow a **narrative arc**. A way to create a narrative arc is by following the story spine by Kenn Adams. [3]

THE STORY SPINE

THE STORY SPINE	STRUCTURE	FUNCTION
Once upon a time...	Beginning	The world of the story is introduced and the main character's routine is established.
Every day...		
But, one day...	The Event	The main character breaks the routine .
Because of that...	Middle	There are dire consequences for having broken the routine. It is unclear if the main character will come out alright in the end.
Because of that...		
Because of that...		
Until finally...	The Climax	The main character embarks upon success or failure
And, ever since then...	End	The main character succeeds or fails, and a new routine is established.

Published at aerogrammestudio.com, ©Kenn Adams

Figure 15: The Story Spine, aerogrammerstudio.com @Kenn Adams

The aim of this **narrative arc** is to

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- 1. Hook the viewer/reader with curiosity:** the problem we are trying to solve matters to everyone.
- 2. Explain how it works:** this is how details and technical explanations come handy.
- 3. Demonstrate credibility and proof:** this is where data comes handy, we are a research project and we can prove our solution works with science.

With a few tweaks, we can apply this scheme to Eclectic’s possible stories, starting with the key message and the target group, such as in the example below.

Target group: Local businesses and businesses associations.

Key message: Through local workshops, SMEs and business will learn to rethink “take-make-waste” production models and identify opportunities to “close the loop” (CiRLabs actions).

Story:

Table 8: Story, Table loosely adapted form Charle Jourdan storytelling process.

Once upon a time...	General problem	What is the global problem you are addressing (at the largest scale possible)?	Our cities consume resources, produce greenhouse gas emissions, and generate waste of resources, energy and water.
Every day...	Specific problem	Think about a specific person* how does this problem affect him/her? *Think back at the target groups and at their problems!	In Trentino South Tyrol over 68% of the waste comes from the construction sector. This means a high cost for the region/province and for the firms themselves.
But, one day...	Expectation	How would Eclectic solve this problem? (what if?)	What if we could reduce the amount of waste generated by the construction industry?
Because of that...	How it works	Eclectic is helping people by...	Eclectic is helping the construction industry by organizing meetings between construction companies, waste management companies and industry associations.

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<p>Until finally...</p>	<p>Proof</p>	<p>What has Eclectic accomplished that proves that?</p>	<p>This sparked a new collaboration to reuse agricultural waste to produce new construction material. This construction material has lower emissions and the process generates less waste than traditional material. It works perfectly to insulate buildings, improving the living comfort of all buildings and especially of low-income families.</p>
<p>And, ever since then...</p>	<p>Vision</p>	<p>What will we the future look like?</p>	<p>More regions need find the opportunities to reduce waste by creating circular economy processes that work in their area, with the framework developed by Eclectic.</p>

This approach can be adapted to the creation of each piece of content: from a social media post to a magazine article, from a video to a newsletter. It can be even used in presentations, events and workshops.

WP4 team will assist partners in developing this kind of narrative in their own channels.

8 Brand voice and writing

The brand voice defines the identity of the brand making it recognisable, just like a person is recognised by both by how he/she dresses and by how he/she talks. It is how a brand talks in channels such as social media, reports and presentations, press releases, videos.

However, since the project will be mainly communicated via the channels of each partner, the Eclectic brand voice will merge with each partners' voice and style.

Therefore, rather than defining a brand voice for the project, we would like to give some **guidelines** that may be useful to all partners to communicate circular economy simply and effectively. This is to make sure that 20+ people working in Eclectic communicate in a consistent and understandable way.

8.1 Writings tips

Good writing is essential to communicate effectively through many channels: social media, newsletter, websites, press releases. For this reason, this document is intended as a guide that partners can apply in their own communication channels.

8.2 Dos and Don'ts

Table 9: Dos and Don'ts

Dos	Don'ts
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keep it short: one information, one sentence. • Frontloading: important information goes first. • Use plain language: make complex things simple. • Use formatting (sub-headings, bullet points, bold) to point out important information. • Focus on the why: why should be anyone interested in your story? • Be precise: present research methodology and outcomes in a clear and precise manner. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid jargon and bureaucratic language. • Avoid technical terms – or explain them simply. • Avoid passive. • Avoid acronyms: if you have to use them, explain them. • Avoid details such as funding information, project partners names and project details at the beginning of a text.

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Stick to the facts, use real-world examples and case studies. Backup statements with informed research.• Show the practical applications of the research, tangible outcomes, tools, and recommendations.• Maintain consistency in the use of terminology across all communication materials.• Use references to let users browse for more information.• Use quotes to add insights and inspire, not to give important information.	
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Looking more broadly at the content, we suggest being:

1. **Positive**: maintain a positive tone to inspire confidence in the potential of circular economy practices.
2. **Transparent**: be honest in communicating both successes and challenges of establishing circular economy practices.
3. **Human-centric**: address the real-world challenges faced by citizens, business owners, local authorities.
4. **Inspirational**: Eclectic should show what the future could look like with widespread adoption of circular economy principles.

8.3 Inverted pyramid and 5W

If you need to **get the media attention**, you must be sure to convey key information first.

The inverted pyramid and the **5W + 1 H approach** are encouraged: structure the news or the press release following the questions listed below.

- Who is the topic about?
- What is the topic about?
- Why does it matter?
- Where does the information occur?
- When did it occur?
- How did it happen?

News report structure: inverted pyramid

Figure 16: Inverted pyramid. The Guardian Foundation [4]

8.4 Taxonomy/Glossary

One of the key aspects is **consistency** in the use of words. For this reason, a **taxonomy/glossary** of circular economy terminology will be developed. This document should be easily **accessible** and understandable even by non-experts.

For example, circular economy could be explained in plain language such as:

Circular economy is a new way of managing resources that focuses on sustainability. It's all about using resources efficiently and making sure materials and products last as long as possible. Unlike the old way of using things and throwing them away, circular economy encourages a cycle where resources are reused, recycled, and repurposed, creating a more sustainable and lasting system.

The outcome could be a **manual** with tips and practical examples, such as in the guides shown below.

Reader's guide: Key definitions

The terms [Citizens' Assembly](#), [sortition](#), [deliberation](#), and [citizen](#) appear regularly throughout this paper and are key to its understanding.

Citizens' Assembly

A Citizens' Assembly is a group of people who are selected through sortition to be broadly representative of a community. They are convened with the aim of making shared, consensus-driven recommendations for decision makers through deliberation. Citizens' Assemblies are sometimes called Citizens' Juries, Panels, or Councils depending on their size and the country where they are taking place.

There are two main ingredients of a Citizens' Assembly that differentiate it from other forms of participation and enable its effectiveness and legitimacy - these are [sortition](#) and [deliberation](#).

For more details on the technical and practical considerations for running a Citizens' Assembly (including how many people to invite and select, an expected budget for running an Assembly, and other key elements) refer to our [Assembling an Assembly Guide here](#).

Figure 17: "Six ways to democratise city planning: Enabling thriving and healthy cities", DemocracyNext [5]

Il tono di voce della nuova rete civica

Per le schede informative sul sito del Comune di Bologna abbiamo scelto di usare un tono di voce informale che si rivolge a un "tu".

A monte c'è il desiderio di sburocratizzare e semplificare il linguaggio amministrativo, ridurre le distanze tra amministrazione e persone destinatarie dei nostri servizi. In molti casi ci permette anche di evitare il maschile generalizzato.

4.2.5 Perifrasi

Laddove possibile consigliamo il ricorso alla tecnica della perifrasi, applicabile nelle formule di saluto delle newsletter o nei messaggi standardizzati, come ad esempio:

✘ Sconsigliato	✔ Consigliato
Benvenuto/Bentornato	Ti diamo il benvenuto/bentornato
Benvenuti/Bentornati	Vi diamo il benvenuto/bentornato

4.2.6 La forma passiva e la forma impersonale

Per completezza, nominiamo altre due strategie che permettono di oscurare il genere, ma ne **sconsigliamo** l'utilizzo. La **forma passiva** e la **forma impersonale** sono espedienti linguisticamente corretti che consentono di rendere il testo

Figure 18: Parole che fanno la differenza, Comune di Bologna [6]

descrizione

L'accordo di aggettivi, participi e pronomi con sostantivi di genere diverso è di norma al maschile plurale. Si può ovviare a questa norma tramite l'accordo di prossimità: se l'ultimo termine di una lista prima dell'aggettivo o del participio è femminile (o maschile) si fa l'accordo al femminile (o maschile)

esempio

Dottorandi e dottorande sono stati proclamati

Dottorandi e dottorande sono state proclamate

Dottorande e dottorandi sono stati proclamati

Glossario

forma femminile	forma maschile	forma astratta / collettiva
L'architetta	L'architetto	
L'autrice	L'autore	
La coordinatrice	Il coordinatore	Il coordinamento / chi coordina
La docente	Il docente	Il corpo docenti
La direttrice	Il direttore	La direzione / chi dirige
L'impiegata amministrativa	L'impiegato amministrativo	Il personale amministrativo
L'ingegnera	L'ingegnere	
La professoressa	Il professore	Il corpo docenti
La ricercatrice	Il ricercatore	Il personale di ricerca
La rappresentante	Il rappresentante	

Figure 19: Guida pratica per una comunicazione inclusiva, Politecnico di Torino [7]

Given the international nature of the project, particular attention should be given to the choice of which **language** to use in the communication activities. This will be largely dependent on the audience of each channel: we invite partners to choose the appropriate language according to each situation and activity, eschewing the dominance of English when the most understandable language is another.

9 Timeline

When to tell the story of Eclectic?

The project Eclectic runs from November 2023 to November 2026. Although the lifecycle lasts 3 years, we expect results to come in the second half of the project duration.

Nevertheless, also the first half of the project duration can provide communication opportunities. We roughly plan to focus on the following aspects of the project.

1. **Year 1: vision and mission.** We set the stage, explain what the problem is we are trying to solve and why we are doing the project. We present the characters.
2. **Year 2: status update.** We gather material of the ongoing activities, we explain the process, and the intermediate results.
3. **Year 3: results and case study.** We show the results in form of case studies, and we document the lessons learned for further projects.

We can roughly plan communication activities based on the expected results stated on the grant agreement. This will need to be adapted according to the evolution of the project.

Figure 20: Eclectic Timeline

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TV/Radio campaign	Number of contacts made during the campaign
Video	Number of views
Website	Number of visits

11 Partnerships and collaborations

Finding and exploiting opportunities to collaborate with other projects is one of the activities of the WP communication.

Eclectic will collaborate with projects funded in the same call, on the topic of Circular Urban Economies Transition Pathway.

Active participation in the events of the DUT community will be a starting point to get to know other projects working on the same objectives. The first of these events will be the DUT Call 2022 Projects Kick-off Event, which will take place between 11 and 12 April 2024 in Brussels.

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